

OF INFORMATION CONSUMPTION CULTURE IN STUDENTS

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***Abstract.** Recently, the tendency to look at the concept of information culture as a whole in the situation of integration of information and culture components of a person is increasing. As a result, information culture is considered as a part of universal culture. It is this view that allows us to reveal the true essence of information culture. This article discusses exactly this issue.*

***Key words:** information consumption, communication, communication, society, globalization, internet system, culture, consumer culture.*

Introduction

Content and essence of the culture of information consumption. The rapid development of information and communication technologies shortens time and distance, opening a wide path to the knowledge of world civilization. If at one time the resources in the libraries of a certain region were used for the sphere of science, culture, education and business, today it will be possible to include all the resources on the Internet in the volume of resources that they can use. The rapid increase in the amount of information resources emerging in society is creating an information storm. We do not believe that all the information in these resources is reliable, based on accurate facts, and serves for the development of society.

Formation of information culture in them is a very urgent problem in protecting society members, especially young people, who are the future of society, from the information storm that is forming in society.

What is information culture and why do we need information culture?

The concept of "information culture" is based on two fundamental concepts: information and culture. Based on this, there are differences in the "culture" and "information" approaches to the interpretation of this concept. Within the framework of the cultural approach, information culture is considered as a way of human life in an information society, as an organizer of the process of human culture formation. In the framework of the information approach, it is considered as a set of knowledge of all information activities aimed at satisfying the information demand.

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The transition of human civilization to the information society has started to create serious problems, such as timely preparation of people for new life conditions and professional activity in a highly automated information environment, teaching them to act independently in this environment, to effectively use the opportunities of the environment, and to protect themselves from negative influences. Problems in the formation of the information society, first of all, the problem of the place of man in this society are today the subject of attention of the international community. The need for special preparation of people for life in the information society is

considered at the summits of prestigious international organizations, and special programs are being adopted. As an example of this

UNESCO's "Information for All" program and IFLA's "Information Literacy" department can be mentioned. It is not difficult to see that the mentioned problems are reflected in the definition of information culture.

The importance of information culture in the educational system

The main reforms in the socio-economic life of the country, in turn, have a great impact on the requirements for graduates of higher education institutions. In the formation of the important aspects for the professional qualification of the graduate in the new conditions, the higher education institution should develop criteria not only for fullness of certain knowledge and skills, but also for enriching one's own knowledge, posing various problems and solving them, offering alternative solutions, choosing the most effective among them. should also be directed to exits. Achieving these goals depends to some extent on the level of information culture.

The structural structure of a person's information readiness is as follows: the ability to express his information needs, form information requests; knowledge of information resources; the ability to know and use the capabilities of libraries; the ability to search for information; information processing knowledge and skills; skills of critical approach to information, understanding and evaluation, and creative use of information; ability to use modern information and communication technologies.

Today, in the world, there is a large amount of information flow, both in the real environment and in the virtual environment, and thus the level of complexity of its search, collection, processing, analysis and synthesis is also increasing. Therefore, in such an information flow today, it is a vital necessity to acquire the skills of adaptation using various information resources. Today's student must acquire a certain information culture, and continuous education and independent education are unthinkable without it. Based on this, while work is being carried out on the improvement of the state educational standards, it is appropriate to make changes in the creation of the standard of the "Information and library science" education course to give the graduate of this course the qualification of a librarian-pedagogue.

The reforms carried out in the field of education in our country put the need to reorganize and improve the activities of libraries of educational institutions based on modern requirements and needs. Because they have to fulfill the important task of receiving, gathering and presenting the strong flow of information that is being created at a time when the educational system is being updated in content and form, and present it to the general public, professors, teachers, students and pupils in the most pleasant ways. These sources of information include, first of all, educational literature, regulatory documents, methodical manuals and other sources directly related to the educational process.

In the process of modernization of education in our republic, rapid informatization of society, establishment of the market of educational publications, and development of information technologies are taking place harmoniously. All this requires the transformation of an integral part of the libraries of educational institutions, a real information supply center, into a base that forms the information culture of a person. It should be noted that every educational institution should receive, process and use the information it needs from the global information network. Previously, great importance was attached to the accumulation of material goods, but now information and

knowledge are becoming the main resources of society, that is, the attitude to information has changed fundamentally, and it has begun to be understood as a strategic resource that stands alongside natural, financial, labor and other resources for the development of society and the state. The description and characteristics of modern information resources, the flow of documents in the information system are increasingly changing. According to the current level of information technology development, paper information carriers are being transferred to electronic media. This applies not only to documents and references, but also to artistic texts, theoretical, pedagogical and methodical literature. The possibility of using the Internet enables the transmission and reception of information at an unprecedented speed, from any point on the Earth.

In conclusion, creating information culture guides in the educational system and harmonizing them with learning management systems is a good way to ensure the effectiveness of the knowledge imparted to students. In addition, if information acquisition culture, i.e. training on information literacy, is included in the curriculum, it would have a great impact on the students' use of quality scientific resources and the improvement of their skills.

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